

THE CHARACTERISTICS OF CARIES FORMATION IN CHILDREN WITH MUSCULOSKELETAL DISORDERS: SUMMARY REVIEW

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Abstract

Dental caries in children is the most common multifactorial oral disease all over the globe. The peculiarity of high dental caries susceptibility of children with the musculoskeletal system disorders lies in the initial disturbance of the process of germinal development of hard tooth enamel and more prominent appearance of cariogenic factors.

Keywords: caries, children, musculoskeletal system disorders.

The term musculoskeletal disorders (MS) is commonly used in medicine. It involves a range of disorders with underdevelopment, impairment or loss of motor function. Childhood caries is a global public health problem affecting all countries of the world [21].

Our research has shown that at school age children with MS disorders (hip dysplasia and congenital hip dislocation, torticollis, clubfoot, syndactyly, polydactyly and other hand and foot abnormalities, etc.) have a high incidence (up to 85%) of dental caries.

The purpose of this summary review is to identify factors that influence the development of dental caries in children with musculoskeletal disorders in order to formulate a strategy for targeted treatment and preventive measures.

Methods. Original research published in scientific databases on the topic has been analysed.

Current research has revealed 114 factors potentially associated with acquired developmental defects and enamel damage leading to the development of dental caries and other dental hard tissue diseases [5]. It is our belief that the development of dental caries in children with MS disorders is also multifactorial, and the initial cause triggering mechanism is their primary systemic disease. Research has revealed that the process of germinal formation and development of dental hard enamel follows a complex dynamic pathway based on the interaction of unique proteins produced by amyloblasts with calcium and phosphate ions [10,16]. The mineral turnover of the foetus and its further dental health is closely related to the maternal calcium and vitamin D status and the metabolism of calcium-regulating hormones in the pregnant woman. Calcium and phosphorus metabolism disorders can be due to intrauterine developmental abnormalities, fetal immaturity, and the presence of genetic defects [17]. Considering caries as one of the systemic effects of metabolic changes in bone tissue, we focused on the interaction between the main mineral-forming elements of bone tissue: calcium, phosphorus, fluorine and magnesium. Fetal dental mineralisation starts in the second trimester of pregnancy. Ca and P compounds in the form of hydroxyapatite $\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$ are the main inorganic mineral component of bone and dental cement, dentin and enamel. It has been proven that high concentrations of calcium and phosphate in plaque or saliva can reduce

bacterial adhesion to enamel and inhibit bacterial biofilm formation [7]. One of the most important mineral elements that influence the development of dental caries is fluoride. Numerous studies have proved that fluoride can increase mineralisation of dental tissue by improving calcium absorption. Notably, when the chemical relationship between fluoride and calcium is impaired, even sufficient calcium cannot be absorbed in the body.[14]. At the same time, Mg, promotes the absorption of Ca in the gastrointestinal tract and also activates alkaline phosphatase, which is involved in hard teeth tissue mineralization [20]. Vitamin D deficiency is an important risk factor for both the incidence of dental caries and its severity in children [3]. Studies have shown that vitamin D deficiency affects odontogenesis, leading to hypomineralisation of the dentition. Apparently therefore, the abnormal structure and morphology of the teeth, due to the improper amelogenesis process and the associated mineralization of the dental enamel germ, may contribute to the occurrence and progression of dental caries [9]. At the same time it is proved that high consumption of magnesium can reduce the risk of vitamin D deficiency. Magnesium regulates the activity of the most important enzymes in vitamin D metabolism. Therefore, magnesium deficiency may adversely affect vitamin D status. [8]. The prevalence of hypomineralisation (MIH) in the study population of schoolchildren in Sudan was 20.1% [1], in Northern Norway 13.9% [18]. Among schoolchildren with MS disorders, we observed MIH affecting one to four first permanent molars in 46% of schoolchildren with prevalent dental caries. The high prevalence of molar- incisal hypomineralisation (MIH) has been associated with pregnancy complications, particularly in the last trimester [9].

The role of nutrition in the risk of dental caries is evident. Feeding behaviour with a preference for eating refined carbohydrate-rich and soft or viscous foods containing insufficient amounts of vitamins A, C, D and various mineral compounds (calcium, phosphates, fluorides) contributes to the cariesogenic situation in the mouth [11].

Saliva can be considered as a biomarker of dental caries [12]. Saliva fluid is associated with the oral cavity microbiome and film formation, as well as for maintaining the oral environment. Thick, sticky and frothy saliva with increased viscosity makes the tooth more

susceptible to caries. Various protective factors against caries are present in saliva such as calcium, inorganic phosphate, pH-increasing substances and antimicrobial agents.

The development of tooth caries is closely linked to the oral cavity microbiota [13]. *Streptococcus mutans* and *Streptococcus sobrinus* act as the main causative agents of dental caries in humans [6]. Lactobacilli are acidogenic and aciduric microorganisms that are associated with the late stages of dental caries, participating in the progression of the disease [4]. It has been shown that under the action of *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* GG present in the oral cavity, the plaque breaks down easily fermentable carbohydrates to form lactic acid, creating a favourable breeding ground for the bacteria [22]. It is of interest that hollow carious lesions may serve as a reservoir for *H. pylori*. However, its detection has been associated with a higher caries status and severity of caries, as the presence of *H. pylori* alters the balance of the plaque ecosystem in favour of *Streptococcus mutans* [19]. Microbiological studies conducted among school-age children with musculoskeletal disorders in Uzbekistan have shown that the main oral flora is represented by *Streptococcus* of different strains with the prevalence of: *Streptococcus salivarius*, *Streptococcus mitis*, *Streptococcus mutans*, *Streptococcus epidermidis*, *Streptococcus aureus*, and *Candida albicans*. This indicated an imbalance in the oral microbiota and an active caries process [2].

Conclusion. The development of dental caries in children with MS disorders is multifactorial, but the initiating factor is genetically mediated abnormalities in dental enamel development.

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